

VOCATIONAL EDUCATION AS A NECESSARY TOOL IN CAREER GUIDANCE

Nargiza Ikromaliyeva Khalilova

Professor at the Public Security University of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Musayeva Madina

Student of Public Security University of the Republic of Uzbekistan

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It is known that any person in the process of choosing a profession is required to have a stock of information related to this field. This process is definitely organized and implemented on the basis of career guidance. Vocational education is a specially organized process aimed at forming knowledge about professions and professional choice. Vocational education gives an opportunity to form important interests and motives specific to the profession. It is also an important condition for the development of aptitudes and abilities for various forms of activity.

Two stages of providing information about professions are distinguished: micro-information and macro-information. The first stage includes information of a general nature that is not related to specific life situations. The latter includes a stock of clarified knowledge.

In this way, professional education means mastering a wide range of knowledge by a person. The source of this knowledge can be the mass media of real people, their own life experience and the professional activities of other individuals. Also, a professional consultant can not only provide the necessary information ready-made or encourage the client to find the information himself. It can help systematize existing knowledge and understand conflicting information [1, 36].

If professional information is carried out within the framework of a separate educational institution and is of a personal referral nature, then this process should be carried out before the previous professional diagnosis.

It should be noted here that professional communication also plays an important role in professional education. It is the person of the student who realizes the knowledge, skills, and qualifications about professions in the process of communication. For this purpose, it requires effective and efficient use of professional communication in the process of career guidance. Therefore, we will focus on the directions of activities carried out within the framework of professional communication.

Vocational educational lesson. Depending on the organization and composition, this form of work allows solving various tasks. In particular, to activate students' interest in learning and choosing their chosen professions, to educate responsible and active attitudes towards choosing a conscious profession, to determine and form the composition of motivation for professional activity, etc.

A professional interview. Unlike the lecture, the conversation is characterized by a less structured and less problem-oriented nature. It can be conducted both individually and in groups.

Career fairs are one of the traditional methods of providing career information. Professional informative excursions form students' knowledge related to the creation of products in production enterprises, organizations, and teach independent work.

Professional meeting. Roundtable discussions and meetings of young people with representatives of various professions are considered one of the ways to increase the research activity of students.

Also, organizing a research work on the definition of professions and organizing a "profession fair" are among the criteria of professional communication. This increases and enriches the level of professional education of students.

At this point, it is worth saying that it is interesting for everyone how to give professional information to a student and from what age to carry out this activity. In particular, in this regard, we would like to briefly touch on the order in which professional education is given at different age levels. As its initial stage, it starts from preschool age and continues until adolescence[2,97].

Preschool age. As we all know, children of senior preschool age begin to get acquainted with the world of professions, and children play them in the process of role-playing games.

Junior school age. The traditional way to learn about professions at school is the labor class.

Adolescence is the first time that choosing a profession becomes an urgent problem at this age.

Parents of teenagers and young adults. When organizing career guidance work with children and adolescents, it should be taken into account that their parents have the main influence on their choices.

In order to effectively implement professional information, a career guidance psychologist should:

- to know the future and current requirements of the region for personnel and production;
- preparation of educational materials in a modern way, i.e. training manuals, career orientation leaflets, etc.
- having a list of recommended literature in the professional direction [2,99].

It can be seen from the given information that guiding young people to choose a conscious profession is one of the most urgent issues. Therefore, it is necessary to inform not only our students, but also pedagogues and parents who have an effective influence on them.

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